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Deliverable 5.4: Report on the biopreservation methods as inhibitors of pathogens in enhanced processes of artisanal foods

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1. Introduction

The selection of the artisanal products and their prototype elaboration process to be tested in fate studies of pathogens were defined within activities performed under Tasks 5.1, 5.2 and 5.3. This proposal is based on the considerations defined in the deliverable 5.3, which particularly described the adapted treatments carried out to assess the effects of the different factors on microbial responses in the fermented food products. In a second stage, this deliverable 5.4 further describes the behavior of foodborne pathogens regarding the changes observed after the application of specific biopreservation methods during fate studies performance with the purpose of enhancing the microbial safety of the fermented artisanal foods tested. The present document may be filled by the different partners belonging to the project, to summarize relevant information about the selected biopreservative method and its application within the performance of the fate studies, as well as the main results obtained so far.

2. Instructions to partners

Partners may summarize the methodologies and particular conditions selected of the biopreservation method to be applied during their fate studies and the main results obtained so far. The following information is required:

Regarding Material and Methods:

- Artisanal food including this relevance information may be affecting to the microbial behaviour.
- Microorganism(s) species and strain(s), concentration inoculated and method of inoculation.
- Biopreservation strategy (EOs, starter cultures) and concentration/ dose applied and method of application.
- Description of microbial fate (e.g., log reduction).
- Comparison with traditional (control) treatment.
- Other factors evaluated and/or measured (e.g., temperature ranges, essential oils type and obtention, origin of lactic acid bacteria evaluated, pH/a_w ranges, etc.).

- Data analysis methods.

Regarding Results:

- Summarize the main results in tables and/or graphs.
- Highlight the trends and main effects observed in the fate studies after the application of the selected biopreservation method.

3. Partner UCO

3.1 Summary of Material & Methods

3.1.1 Starter culture addition in fresh cheese manufacturing

A lab-scale fresh goat cheese was elaborated following the main production steps and orientations of an artisanal cheese producer located in Málaga (Spain) (**Figure 1**). The ingredients used for cheese elaboration were pasteurized goat milk, salt (NaCl, 10%v/v), calcium chloride (CaCl₂, 0.28%v/v) and rennet (0.28%v/v). The commercial starter cultures used for cheese elaboration were composed by *Lactococcus lactis* subsp. *lactis*, *Lactococcus lactis* subsp. *cremoris* and *Streptococcus thermophilus* strains.

Cheese samples of 10 g placed in Falcon tubes were inoculated with a three-strain cocktail of *L. monocytogenes* at 10²-10³ cfu/g. Inoculation was carried out with the aid of a pipette and the inoculum was placed inside the samples (i.e., perforation in the central point). The inoculated strains were isolated from clinical cases and obtained from the Spanish Type Culture Collection (CECT 4032, CECT5366, CECT935). The inoculated samples were stored at different storage temperatures of 4 and 25°C and withdrawn at proper intervals up to 10 days for microbial analysis. The temperature range selected reflect both the optimal logistic distribution chain conditions (4°C) and extreme abuse ones (25°C). *L. monocytogenes* and lactic acid bacteria (LAB) were detected and quantified by ISO methods (ISO 11290 and ISO 15214, respectively). Samples were analysed

in duplicate, and the experiments were repeated twice. The pH and a_w of samples were also measured over storage.

Figure 1. Scheme of the methodology applied to obtain the fresh goat cheese samples.

3.1.2 Starter culture addition in dry-cured fermented sausages manufacturing

Salchichón is a dry-cured fermented sausage classified as a ready-to-eat (RTE) product and is particularly linked to artisanal manufacturing practices in Andalusia (Spain). Lab-scale *salchichón* prototypes (80g) were manufactured with formulated meat batter stuffed into permeable plastic bags by vacuum-packaging (30-35mm Ø). The formulation was composed by pork meat (95% approximately) and a mixture of species and additives such as sugars (dextrose), salt (2.5%) and others, such as sodium nitrite (0.012%). This formulation was provided directly by an artisanal producer located in Granada (Spain) that also offered technical guidance for the main production steps.

A portion of the formulated meat batter was inoculated with a previously reconstituted starter culture (composed by *Lactobacillus curvatus* monoculture, ca. $\approx 6-7$ log cfu/g). The remain batter was used for the production of control samples (only containing the autochthonous meat microbiota including LAB). The manufactured *salchichón* samples were separately inoculated with a three-strain cocktail of *L. monocytogenes* and *Salmonella* spp. (ca. $\approx 6-7$ log cfu/g), previously temperature-adapted (15 °C for 5d) grown in modified TSB containing salt (25g/kg) and sodium nitrite (0.15g/kg). All the inoculated *L. monocytogenes* strains were isolated from fermented food products (i.e., CECT 4032, among others), meanwhile *Salmonella* spp. strains were obtained from the Spanish Type Culture Collection (CECT556, CECT704 and CECT4396). During samples ripening (15d, 16 °C, 70% RH), physicochemical parameters (pH, a_w) and microbial populations (LAB and pathogens) were monitored. Principal kinetic parameters were determined by fitting the Baranyi model to data using the DMFit software.

Figure 2. Scheme of the methodology applied to obtain the lab-scale *salchichón* prototype.

3.2 Summary of Results

3.2.1 Effect of stater culture addition in fresh goat milk cheeses

The results obtained for the assessing of the starter culture effects on the *L. monocytogenes* behaviour in fresh goat milk cheeses are represented in **Figure 3**. Slight variations on the pathogen concentration were observed under storage at 4 °C. The average *L. monocytogenes* concentrations during 10 days of storage at this temperature was of 4.67 ± 0.32 log cfu/g. However, the observed behaviour was different considering 25 °C, showing a slight count increase from 4.48 to 4.60 log cfu/g during the first two days but later decreasing to 1.70 log cfu/g after 10 days of storage. In

samples stored at both temperatures, LAB concentrations were similar over 7 days of time, with ranges of 9.06-9.66 log cfu/g at 4 °C and 9.09-9.61 log cfu/g at 25 °C. However, differences were observed in the last 3 days in samples at 25°C where the LAB concentrations started to decrease in counts, while LAB concentrations remain stable at 4 °C (9.69 log cfu/g).

Figure 3. *L. monocytogenes* concentrations (log cfu/g) obtained in fresh goat milk cheeses during 10 days of storage at 4 °C and 25 °C.

Overall, the pH of samples dropped while the a_w of samples did not vary over storage. The pH dropped from 6.46 to 5.17 at 4 °C, showing the fastest decrease during the first two days, from values of 6.46 to 5.66 (**Figure 4**). This initial decrease was faster at 25 °C, reaching a pH value of 4.98 after two days and dropping to 4.92 after 10 days of storage.

In general, growth rates of *L. monocytogenes* and LAB increased with the increase in storage temperature. However, *L. monocytogenes* maximum population density decreased by increasing storage temperatures. This could be associated with the competition between the pathogen and LAB (i.e., Jameson effect). The decrease of pH was faster at higher temperatures due to the higher LAB growth rate and lactic acid production.

Figure 4. Physicochemical values obtained for pH in fresh goat milk cheeses along 10 days of storage at 4 °C and 25 °C.

3.2.2 Effect of starter culture addition in dry-cured fermented sausages

The results obtained for the assessing of the starter culture effects on the *Salmonella* spp. and *L. monocytogenes* behaviour in *salchichón* are represented in **Figures 5** and **6**.

Salmonella spp. was able to grow in control samples with autochthonous LAB showing a mean population increase of 1.05 log cfu/g (maximum ca. 8.25 log cfu/g) (**Figure 5, A**). However, *Salmonella* spp. growth was inhibited in *salchichón* samples added with LAB starter cultures (**Figure 5, B**).

Figure 5. *Salmonella* spp. (red coloured line) concentrations (log cfu/g) obtained in *salchichón* ripened along 15 days both in control samples (A) with autochthonous lactic acid bacteria (yellow coloured line) and samples added with starter culture (B) in combination with autochthonous lactic acid bacteria (orange coloured).

Figure 6. *Listeria monocytogenes* (green coloured line) concentrations (log cfu/g) obtained in *salchichón* ripened along 15 days both in control samples (A) with autochthonous lactic acid bacteria (yellow coloured line) and samples added with starter culture (B) in combination with autochthonous lactic acid bacteria (orange coloured).

The growth ability of *L. monocytogenes* was shown both in added and non-added starter culture samples. The results obtained in control samples showed a *L. monocytogenes* growth potential of 1.96 log cfu/g, a maximum growth rate of 0.008 ± 0.003 log cfu/g/h and reached a maximum population of 7.77 log cfu/g (**Figure 6, A**). However, the effect of the starter culture addition was shown by the extension of *L. monocytogenes* lag phase to 150.02 hours and the reduction of the growth potential (1.70 log cfu/g), maximum population reached and maximum growth rate (0.011 ± 0.007 log cfu/g/h) respect to the results obtained in control samples (**Figure 6, B**).

Figure 7. Tendencies of pH values obtained in two analysis repetitions both of control samples (grey coloured line) and starter cultured added samples (orange coloured line) during ripening of *salchichón*.

Regarding LAB behaviour, homogeneous LAB populations were obtained at the final of the ripening stage (from 8.71 to 9.18 log cfu/g), regardless of the sample type and differences in initial LAB concentrations (≈ 4 and 7 log cfu/g in non-added and added starter cultures samples, respectively). In this sense, accurate molecular detection of the LAB strains should be conducted at various stages of the ripening process to provide a more comprehensive understanding of the specific behavior exhibited by each LAB strains present in the introduced starter culture (e.g., identification of dominant populations). This need is reinforced since values and patterns of the physicochemical values obtained were also very similar in both types of samples. This fact was positive from a technological point of view since the addition of the starter culture did not evidence changes on the physicochemical parameters of pH and a_w respect to the autochthonous LAB. In

this sense, pH described a decrease in values from 5.60-5.65 to 5.20-5.32 and later slightly increased to 5.84, evidencing the previously reported effect in literature of the accumulation of non-protein nitrogen and products of amino acid catabolism (**Figure 7**). Similarly, final a_w values were around 0.960 in both types of samples, showing similar decreasing patterns (**Figure 8**).

Figure 8. Tendencies of average a_w values obtained in control samples (grey coloured line) and starter cultured added samples (orange coloured line) during ripening of *salchichón*.

4. Partner IPB

4.1 Summary of Material & Methods

4.1.1 Bio-intervention strategies tested in *alheira* raw sausage

Staphylococcus aureus (ATCC 6538) maintained on a slant was cultivated overnight in brain heart infusion broth (BHI) at 37 °C. On the day of preparing the *alheiras*, the pre- inoculum (~9.0 log CFU/mL) was diluted in sterile saline water to reach 7.0 log CFU/mL. Four batches of *alheiras* proxy were prepared by soaking wheat white bread (22%) that was previously shredded, in hot boiled water (60%) for 20 min. After breaking down, garlic powder (1%), red pepper powder (1%), salt (1%), and shredded cooked chicken meat (10%) were added and integrated to form the *alheira* batter. Virgin olive oil (5%) was then warmed up to ~50 °C and incorporated with 0.0, 0.5, 1.0 or 1.5% (w/w) of each of the lyophilised extracts (namely, sage, black cumin and annatto extracts).

The oil, still warm, was added to the *alheira* batter. The mixed batter was stuffed in clean pig casings to make mini-*alheiras* of ~80 g. The weight in g of each *alheira* was taken (W), and subsequently each of them was individually inoculated with $10W \mu\text{L}$ using a sterile syringe. This standard procedure produced *alheiras* with *S. aureus* concentration of $\sim 5.0 \log \text{CFU/g}$. The same batches of *alheira* were produced as negative controls (no *S. aureus* inoculated), in order to avail of samples to analyse the physicochemical properties of *alheiras* during maturation. *Alheiras* were hung in a climate controlled chamber (10 °C, 85% RH) for maturation to take place during 12-13 days. Lactic acid bacteria and *S. aureus* were counted on MRS and Baird-Parker agar according to ISO methods, at least on 6 time points in duplicate.

4.1.2 Bio-intervention strategies tested in goat's raw milk cheese manufacturing

Laboratory-scale cheeses were prepared by adding the rennet (0.75 mL/L milk) and *S. aureus* inoculum (5 mL/L milk) to milk at approximately 34 °C, in the case of challenge tests with plant extracts; or rennet (0.75 mL/L milk), *S. aureus* inoculum (5 mL/L milk) and selected LAB cocktail inoculum (10 mL/L milk, 1% (v/v)), in the case of challenge tests with added starter culture. Through this procedure, each cheese reached a *S. aureus* target concentration of 4 to 5 log CFU/g, depending on the milk initial contamination. After 30 minutes at 34 °C, curdled milk was cut and drained, and, for challenge tests with plant extracts, 1% (w/w) of lyophilised spearmint, lemon balm or sage extract was added to the curd and mixed. An inoculated control without extract or without starter culture was kept. Non-inoculated cheeses with starter culture were also produced.

Next, the curd was placed in 50 mL tubes and centrifuged at 6000 rpm at 20 °C for 3.5 minutes. The supernatant (whey) was removed, and cheeses of approximately 5 g were cut from the compacted curd and placed in a 15% (w/v) brine solution (ratio cheese: brine of approximately 90 g: 1.5L) for 10 minutes at 25 °C for salting. Finally, the weight in g of each cheese was annotated and cheeses were kept in a climate-controlled chamber (10 °C, 98% RH) for fermentation and maturation to take place for 15 days. Lactic acid bacteria and *S. aureus* were counted on MRS and Baird-Parker agar according to ISO methods, at least on 6 time points in duplicate.

4.2 Summary of Results

4.2.1 Effect of bio-intervention strategies in *alheira* raw sausage manufacturing

The challenge tests performed in *alheira* sausage, testing the efficacy of bio-intervention strategies, showed that the three plant-based hydroethanolic extracts (i.e., sage, black cumin, annatto) added in the three doses (0.5, 1.0, 1.5%) reduced the populations of *S. aureus* during maturation, in comparison to the control (no extract added to the batter) (**Table 1**). In all cases, the greater the dose, the higher the reduction effect of *S. aureus*. However, among the three types of extracts, black cumin presented the least effectiveness. The antimicrobial effect of sage and annatto extract against *S. aureus* was comparable (at a dose of 1.0%, mean log reductions were 0.837 and 0.836 log CFU/g, respectively); nonetheless, both extracts also delayed the development of LAB, causing a lower concentration of LAB by the end of maturation. Sage extract presented a higher reduction effect of LAB (1.919 log CFU/g at 0.5%; 3.332 log CFU/g at 1.0%; and 3.963 log CFU/g at 1.5%) than annatto extract (0.403 log CFU/g at 0.5%; 2.570 log CFU/g at 1.0%; and 3.432 log CFU/g at 1.5%; **Table 1**).

Table 1. Mean reduction in *S. aureus* and in lactic acid bacteria (LAB) concentration attained by the use of plant-based extracts or added selected lactic acid bacteria at the end of maturation of *alheira* sausages, in comparison to the controls (no bio-intervention strategy applied)

Bio-intervention	Dose in batter	Reduction in <i>S. aureus</i> (log CFU/g)	Reduction in LAB (log CFU/g)
Sage extract	0.5%	0.705	1.919
	1.0%	0.837	3.332
	1.5%	0.950	3.963
Black cumin extract	0.5%	0.117	0.140
	1.0%	0.236	0.170
	1.5%	0.309	0.820
Annatto extract	0.5%	0.632	0.403
	1.0%	0.836	2.570
	1.5%	1.033	3.432
<i>Lactobacillus</i> strain 1	7.0 log CFU/g	0.840	- ^a
<i>Lactobacillus</i> strain 2	7.0 log CFU/g	0.810	-
<i>Lactococcus</i> strain 1	7.0 log CFU/g	0.480	-
<i>Lactococcus</i> strain 2	7.0 log CFU/g	0.205	-

^a Addition of strains cause increase in LAB and not reduction

Furthermore, challenge studies were undertaken to evaluate the antimicrobial effect of selected lactic acid bacteria. LAB isolates had been isolated and characterised in Work Package 3 of the ArtiSaneFood project; and a selection of the most promising LABs were obtained. Among the four LAB tested, the addition of *Lactobacillus* strain 1 or 2 at a concentration of ~ 7.0 log CFU/g in batter produced a drop in *S. aureus* in 0.840 and 0.810 log CFU/g by the end of maturation, in comparison to the controls (no addition of LAB) (Table 1).

Whereas the addition of annatto did not significantly affect the evolution of pH during maturation (**Figure 9**), the use of the added *Lactobacillus* strains did produce a steeper drop in pH (**Figure 10**), as a result of the faster fermentation taking place. There was no significant difference in pH drop in *alheira* between the two *Lactobacillus* strains added.

Figure 9. Evolution of pH in *alheiras* during maturation. *Alheiras* formulated with 1.0% annatto and 0.0% annatto (control) did not differ significantly and was modelled by the single equation shown

Among the bio-intervention strategies assessed, the most effective against *S. aureus* turned out to be the formulation of the sausage with annatto extract at 1.0% and the addition of *Lactobacillus* strain 1, 2 (or a mixture). These bio-intervention strategies did not affect the overall organoleptic properties. On the contrary, the annatto extract produced *alheiras* of more intense reddish colour.

Figure 10. Evolution of pH in *alheiras* during maturation. *Alheiras* with added *Lactobacillus* strains 1 and 2 produced a pH profile significantly different from the control (no added LAB)

4.2.2 Effect of bio-intervention strategies in goat's raw milk cheese manufacturing

In the case of the challenge tests undertaken for goat's raw milk cheesemaking, the level of *S. aureus* reduction due to the addition of plant extracts was comparable to that attained in the *alheira* sausages: in most cases they were below 1.0 log CFU/g reduction by the end of maturation (**Table 2**). Among the three extracts, spearmint extract exerted the highest reduction effect in *S. aureus* population and the lowest in LAB (which is a desirable characteristic). Nevertheless, unlike the challenge studies conducted in *alheira* sausage, the added LAB cocktail (mixture of 4 strains) was not as effective as the addition of spearmint for the control of *S. aureus*, having reached a reduction effect of only 0.293 log CFU/g in comparison to the control by the end of maturation (**Table 2**).

Table 2. Mean reduction in *S. aureus* and in lactic acid bacteria (LAB) concentration attained by the use of plant-based extracts or added selected lactic acid bacteria at the end of maturation of goat's raw milk cheese, in comparison to the controls (no bio-intervention strategy applied)

Bio-intervention	Dose in curd/milk	Reduction in <i>S. aureus</i> (log CFU/g)	Reduction in LAB (log CFU/g)
Spearmint	1.0%	0.832	0.220
Lemon balm	1.0%	0.349	0.540
Sage	1.0%	0.396	0.560
LAB cocktail (4 strains)	7.0 log CFU/g	0.293	- ^a

^a Addition of strains cause increase in LAB population and not reduction

Thus, among the bio-intervention strategies assessed, the most effective against *S. aureus* turned out to be the formulation of the cheese with spearmint hydroethanolic extract at 1.0%. As can be seen in **Figure 11**, the addition of such extract slightly affected the pH profile of the cheeses during maturation, producing both a slightly slower drop rate and a slightly higher final pH. The effect of adding spearmint extract in the curd on the sensory characteristics of the cheese was not evaluated.

Figure 11. Evolution of pH in goat's raw milk cheeses without (left) and with addition of 1.0% spearmint, during the first 15 days of maturation, described by an empirical decay function.

5. Partner UIZ

5.1. Summary of Material & Methods

5.1.1. Starter culture addition in fresh sausage *Merguez* manufacturing

Merguez is a type of spicy, fresh sausage that is primarily produced through artisanal methods in Morocco. Notably, its preparation does not involve the use of drying or partial drying techniques. The sausage batter, amounting to two kilograms, was formulated with 80% lean beef, 20% beef fat, and a mixture of spices and additives including sugars (dextrose), salt (2.5%), and olive oil. The concoction was mixed for five minutes at 4 °C before being portioned into four experimental batches:

- (i) Control (Batch 1): This included the formulated meat batter without the incorporation of any starter culture.

(ii) Batch 2: This variant of the formulated meat batter was inoculated with a reconstituted starter culture, comprising *Enterococcus durans* Y17 monoculture (approximately 7-8 log cfu/g).

(iii) Batch 3: The meat batter was inoculated with a reconstituted starter culture, this time consisting of *Lactobacillus sakei* Y252 monoculture (approximately 7-8 log cfu/g).

(iv) Batch 4: The formulated meat batter was inoculated with a reconstituted starter culture composed of a coculture of *L. sakei* and *E. durans* (approximate concentration of 7-8 log cfu/g).

The uniformly mixed inoculated batter (300 g) from each batch was subdivided into two 150 g portions, each independently inoculated with a three-strain cocktail of *L. monocytogenes* (approximately 6-7 log cfu/g). The inoculated *L. monocytogenes* strains, procured from the Spanish Type Culture Collection (CECT 5725, CECT 7467, and CECT 4032), were then integrated into the sausage batters. Post-inoculation, the sausage batters were filled into natural casings and stored at two distinct temperatures of 8° and 16°C.

Throughout the storage period, physicochemical parameters (pH, a_w) alongside microbial populations (LAB and *Listeria* spp.) were consistently monitored. The kinetic parameters were evaluated using the Baranyi model applied to the collected data through the DMFit software.

5.1.2. Oregano EO addition in simulated sausage medium (SSM)

In this experiment, a simulated sausage medium was developed by modifying Brain Heart Infusion (BHI) with the inclusion of dextrose, yeast extract, bacteriological agar and Tween 80. Sodium phosphate buffer was employed to adjust the pH to required levels, whereas NaCl was added pre-sterilisation to achieve the desired concentrations. Following the sterilisation, the BHI was supplemented with oregano essential oil (EO) in specified concentrations (see **D5.5**) and inoculated aseptically with a *Salmonella* cocktail including strains *S. kentucky*, *S. hadar* (isolated from the fresh sausage), and the Spanish Type Culture Collection (CECT 704). Following inoculation, samples, each of 10 mL, were aseptically transferred into sterile 50 mL polypropylene conical tubes and permitted to solidify, and incubated at temperatures of 8, 14, and 20°C.

Bacterial counts (transformed to log₁₀), were plotted against time in hours. The survival kinetics of *Salmonella* spp. in SSM were analysed using the Weibull model.

5.1.3. Behaviour of *Staphylococcus aureus* in *Jben* fresh cheese

The laboratory-scale preparation of fresh goat's cheese (*Jben*) was conducted as detailed in **Figure 12**. Ten L of goats' milk was distributed into five bottles with 2 L/bottle, pasteurised at 65 °C for 30 min, and rapidly cooled to 34 °C. For coagulation, calcium chloride (CaCl₂, 0.05% w/v) and rennet (0.03% v/v) were used, following the main production steps of a cheese producer located in Marrakech, without using starter culture. The curds were cut into 8–15 mm cubes and transferred into small-perforated plastic molds overnight at 4 °C to drain off the whey. The *Jben* was next salted (2%) and mixed for 5 min.

Figure 12. Flow chart of the methodology followed to produce the fresh goat cheese samples.

After salting, 10-g cheese samples were placed in sterilized petri dishes (60 mm x 15 mm) and inoculated with a single strain of *S. aureus* (CECT 976) at 10^{2-3} cfu/g. The parafilm was used to

cover the petri dishes and stored at different temperatures (8, 20, 30, and 37 °C) for 19 days (product shelf-life).

For bacteriological analysis, cheese samples were taken at different intervals depending on the temperature of storage and serially diluted to determine *S. aureus* and LAB populations by standard plate count methods. *S. aureus* was enumerated on Braid Parker agar after incubation at 37 °C for 48 h, and LAB were counted on MRAS agar after 48 h of incubation at 30 °C. Samples were analysed in duplicate and the experiments were repeated three times.

The pH and a_w of cheese samples stored at different temperatures were also monitored during storage. The initial pH of samples ranged between 6.38 and 7.05, while the a_w values were around 0.906.

5.1.4. Starter culture addition in fresh cheese manufacturing

The method shown in Figure 1 is used to prepare fresh goat's cheese (*Jben*) on a laboratory scale. In the following steps, *L. monocytogenes* strains (CECT 4032, CECT 935, and CECT 7467) were inoculated at 3 Log into 10 g of cheese samples placed on sterilized petri plates (60 mm x 15 mm). We covered the petri dishes with parafilm, which was then maintained at various temperatures for 19 days (4, 20, 25, and 30 °C).

In order to perform a bacteriological analysis, cheese samples were taken at various intervals and serially diluted in order to determine the number of LAB and *L. monocytogenes*. *L. monocytogenes* was counted on Oxford agar after 24–48 hours at 37°C, and LAB were counted on MRS agar after 48 hours at 30°C. A duplicate sample was examined. In addition, pH and a_w of cheese samples were monitored during storage.

5.2. Summary of Results

5.2.1. Effect of stater culture addition in fresh sausage Merguez

Figures 13, 14, and 15 demonstrate the impact of starter culture on *L. monocytogenes* behaviour in *Merguez*, observed at two different temperatures: 8°C and 16°C. In the control samples (**Figure 13**), autochthonous lactic acid bacteria (LAB) multiplied to approximately 9 log CFU/g at both temperatures, yet *L. monocytogenes* was not effectively inhibited. However, the growth of *L.*

monocytogenes was notably reduced in *Merguez* samples that incorporated LAB starter cultures (Figures 14 and 15).

Figure 13. Concentrations of *L. monocytogenes* in *Merguez* control samples with autochthonous lactic acid bacteria: (A) stored at 8°C and (B) stored at 16°C.

The control samples revealed a *L. monocytogenes* growth potential of 0.71 log cfu/g, a maximum growth rate of 0.017 ± 0.003 log cfu/g/h, and a maximum population of 5.43 log cfu/g (Figure 13, B). At 16°C, *L. monocytogenes* growth was suppressed in batches 2 and 3 when the LAB starter culture achieved its maximum population density (Figure 14B and 15B). For instance, the impact of *L. sakei* Y252 addition was evident in the reduction of growth potential (0.53 log cfu/g), maximum population, and maximum growth rate (0.011 ± 0.007 log cfu/g/h) when compared with the control sample results (Figure 15, B). Furthermore, at a storage temperature of 8°C, *L. sakei* demonstrated an inhibitory effect on *L. monocytogenes* (-0.008 ± 0.002) (Figure 15, A).

Figure 14. *L. monocytogenes* concentrations in *Merguez* samples inoculated with *E. durans* Y17 alongside autochthonous lactic acid bacteria, under different storage temperatures: (A) 8°C and (B) 16°C.

Figure 15. *L. monocytogenes* concentrations in *Merguez* samples inoculated with *L. sakei* Y252 alongside autochthonous lactic acid bacteria, under different storage temperatures: (A) 8°C and (B) 16°C.

After 144 hours of monitoring, we observed similar LAB populations (ranging from 7.56 to 9.47 log cfu/g). This uniformity is remarkable given the significant variations in starter cultures and temperature conditions (8°C and 16°C). Indeed, it is noteworthy that the starter culture had a

negligible impact on the physicochemical characteristics (pH and water activity) of the sample stored at 8°C. Nevertheless, a reduction in pH values was observed at 16 °C (**Figure 16**), which aligns with the accumulation of non-protein nitrogen and products of amino acid metabolism.

Figure 16. Tendencies of pH values obtained in starter cultured added samples during storage of *Merguez* at two different temperatures.

The data gathered from these observations substantiate the potential of LAB for the development of microbial growth models pertinent to fresh sausage safety. However, a more in-depth, strain-specific analysis might provide more detailed insights. Interpretation of these findings should be approached with caution, as unidentified variables could influence LAB behaviour. Future studies would benefit from detailing parameters such as specific bacterial population units and initial concentrations of starter cultures, as these considerations could improve the precision and reliability of the findings.

5.2.2. Impact of oregano essential oil on fresh sausage *Merguez*.

Twenty-three survival curves were produced using the Weibull model to analyse *Salmonella* spp. inactivation in SSM under varying salt (NaCl), pH, temperature, and oregano essential oil (OEO) conditions are presented in **Figure 17**.

Evaluating δ Weibull parameter, e.g. time required for the first log reduction, was considerably lower in SSM containing high concentrations of OEO, indicating that higher concentrations favoured early inactivation of *Salmonella* spp. In addition, the higher the storage temperature and the higher the NaCl, the lower the δ , indicating that raising the temperature up to room temperature with a high NaCl concentration contributed to the pathogen's inactivation.

Despite the fact that *Salmonella* spp. is a mesophilic bacterium, it can tolerate a minimum temperature of 5°C. Based on this tolerance, the strain tested was found to be resistant to refrigerated conditions, as indicated by the pattern of bacteria counts for samples stored at 8°C (Figure 17, B and C). The refrigeration process is typically used to store perishable foods. However, refrigeration cannot prevent *Salmonella* spp. from growing if it has been contaminated initially. Natural preservation hurdles, such as essential oils, may provide an effective method of ensuring food safety for highly perishable foods kept under refrigeration during their shelf life.

Figure 17. Inactivation of *Salmonella* spp. on simulated sausage medium combined with OEO application at different concentrations. 0.3% (A); 0.15% (B); 0.075% (C). Weibull model fit (solid lines).

5.2.3. Behaviour of *S. aureus* in Jben fresh cheese

Growth of the *S. aureus* population in fresh goat's cheese during different storage temperatures is reported in **Tables 3, 4, 5 and 6**. In general, fresh cheese supported significant growth of *S. aureus* at all temperatures evaluated.

In samples stored at 8 °C, the *S. aureus* population reached a maximum average concentration of 8.21 log cfu/g at the end of storage. Similarly, the same behavior was observed for the LAB population, reaching 9.25 log cfu/g after 19 days of storage.

Table 3: Results obtained from the analysis of fresh goat cheese stored at 8°C for 19 days.

Time (days)	0	1	2	6	8	14	19
<i>S. aureus</i> (log cfu/g)	2.84±0.53	4.38±0.9	5.51±1.1	6.09±0.89	7.15±1.16	7.54±0.6	8.21±0.19
LAB (log cfu/g)	3.51±0.46	6.00±0.09	6.26±0.8	6.79±0.57	8.33±0.66	8.19±0.7	9.25±0.18
pH	6.14±0.24	6.53±0.61	6.48±0.30	6.19±0.10	6.31±0.02	6.38±0.48	6.74±0.24

At 20 °C, the *S. aureus* population was about 8.08 log cfu/g after 8 days of storage, while this population level was observed after 19 days of storage at 8 °C. On the other hand, the LAB population was approximately 9 log cfu/g after 2 days of storage.

Table 4: Results obtained from the analysis of fresh goat cheese stored at 20°C for 19 days.

Time (days)	0	1	2	6	8	14	19
<i>S. aureus</i> (log cfu/g)	2.84±0.53	6.46±0.47	6.98±0.49	7.58±0.53	8.08±0.48	8.70±0.14	8.42±0.11
LAB (log cfu/g)	3.51±0.46	7.20±0.45	8.98±0.27	9.54±0.08	9.37±0.03	8.74±0.70	9.34±0.54
pH	6.14±0.24	6.08±0.31	5.79±0.28	5.47±0.14	5.44±0.12	6.15±0.01	7.60±0.40

When samples were stored at 30 °C and 37 °C, the *S. aureus* population was approximately 5 log cfu/g after 6 h, reaching close to 7 log cfu/g after one day of storage. No difference in counts was observed between samples stored at 30 and 37 °C after 4 days of storage, except that samples stored at 37 °C showed early spoilage after 4 days of storage, while the *S. aureus* population stored at 30 °C reached a maximum average concentration of 8.08 log cfu/g after 8 days of storage. LAB growth was similar at 30 and 37 °C, with growth accelerating in the first hours of storage and reaching a maximum average concentration of 9.52 and 9.31 log cfu/g after 4 days at 30 and 37 °C, respectively.

Table 5: Results obtained from the analysis of fresh goat cheese stored at 30°C for 8 days.

Time (days)	0	0.25	1	2	4	6	8
<i>S. aureus</i> (log cfu/g)	2.84±0.53	5.08±0.89	6.99±0.26	6.80±0.18	7.17±0.48	7.64±0.43	8.06±0.40
LAB (log cfu/g)	3.51±0.46	6.70±0.62	8.88±0.25	9.30±0.26	9.52±0.30	9.28±0.16	9.49±0.09
pH	6.14±0.24	6.08±0.28	6.10±0.32	5.46±0.16	5.29±0.19	5.79±0.14	6.55±0.25

Table 6: Results obtained from the analysis of fresh goat cheese stored at 37°C for 4 days.

Time (days)	0	0.25	0.42	1	2	4
<i>S. aureus</i> (log cfu/g)	2.84±0.53	5.68±0.43	6.33±0.60	6.98±0.48	6.88±0.28	7.11±0.18
LAB (log cfu/g)	3.51±0.46	6.55±0.09	6.91±1.15	9.18±0.37	9.18±0.16	9.31±0.52
pH	6.14±0.24	6.11±0.31	5.90±0.30	5.77±0.20	5.47±0.05	5.57±0.21

The pH values of cheese decreased from 6.14 to 5.44 after 6 days of storage at 20 °C, while no significant changes were observed in cheese stored at 8 °C. After 4 days of storage at 30 and 37 °C, the pH values of the cheese decreased from an initial mean value of 6.14 to 5.29 and 5.57, respectively. Also, the pH increased over time until the end of the storage period for cheese stored at 20 and 30 °C. This increase in pH may be due to microbial proteases producing peptides, amino acids, and nitrogenous substances that affect the organic acids generated by LAB. However, the a_w remained almost stable during the storage period.

Generally, *Jben* supported faster growth of *S. aureus* over storage time, and as the temperature increased, a shorter time was required to reach a stationary phase. However, no significant competition was found between the *S. aureus* and LAB populations.

5.2.4. Starter culture addition in fresh cheese manufacturing

Growth of the *L. monocytogenes* population in fresh goat's cheese during different storage temperatures is reported in **Tables 7, 8, 9 and 10**.

In samples stored at 4 °C, the *L. monocytogenes* population reached a maximum average concentration of 6.54 log cfu/g at 480 h. The same behavior was observed for the LAB population, reaching 6.37 log cfu/g after 20 days of storage.

Table 7: Results obtained from the analysis of fresh goat cheese stored at 4°C for 20 days.

Time (hours)	0	24	48	144	240	312	480
<i>L. monocytogenes</i> (log cfu/g)	3.32	3.59	3.92	4.79	5.74	6.07	6.54
LAB (log cfu/g)	2.59	3.78	4.29	4.60	5.65	6.01	6.37
pH	6.758	6.784	6.675	6.564	6.49	6.474	6.373

At 20 °C, the *L. monocytogenes* population reached 7.30 log cfu/g after 48 h of storage. This population level was approximately reached after 480 h of storage at 4 °C. On the other hand, the LAB population was approximately 9 log cfu/g after 240 h of storage.

Table 8: Results obtained from the analysis of fresh goat cheese stored at 20°C for 20 days.

Time (hours)	0	24	48	144	240	312	480
<i>L. monocytogenes</i> (log cfu/g)	3.32	6.12	7.30	8.41	8.44	9.41	8.80
LAB (log cfu/g)	2.59	6.92	7.97	8.40	9.12	9.69	9.29
pH	6.758	6.545	6.544	6.321	6.686	5.982	6.132

After 24 hours of storage at 20°C, 25°C, and 30°C, the *L. monocytogenes* population was approximately 6 log cells/g, reaching close to 7 log cells/g after one day. There was no significant difference in LAB growth at 20 °C, 25 °C, and 30 °C. During the first few hours of storage, growth increased rapidly and a maximum average concentration of 9 log CFU/g was reached.

Table 9: Results obtained from the analysis of fresh goat cheese stored at 25°C for 96 hours.

Time (hours)	0	4	10	24	30	48	96
<i>L. monocytogenes</i> (log cfu/g)	3.32	6.80	7.08	7.53	8.08	8.82	8.63
LAB (log cfu/g)	2.59	7.02	8.57	8.45	8.99	9.13	7.70
pH	6.758	6.42	6.419	6.112	5.973	6.523	8.177

Table 10: Results obtained from the analysis of fresh goat cheese stored at 30°C for 96 hours.

Time (hours)	0	4	10	24	30	96
<i>L. monocytogenes</i> (log cfu/g)	3.32	7.37	8.25	7.90	8.57	8.27
LAB (log cfu/g)	2.59	7.87	7.36	8.97	8.88	9.51
pH	6.758	6.391	6.671	6.478	7.01	8.213

6. Partner ISBST/UMA

6.1. Summary of Material & Methods for Fermented Dried Sausage

The laboratory-scale preparation of artisanal dry sausages was performed according to the traditional Tunisian recipe and was conducted as detailed in **Figure 18**. After mincing the raw beef meat (80% lean) purchased from a local supermarket, in Braganca, salt (1.8%), hot paste Harissa and other spices including coriander caraway, red pepper, fennel seeds powder, dried mint and garlic were added to the batter. All the condiments were used by Tunisian local producer for sausage preparation. To ensure microbial safety of the condiments, they were irradiated beforehand.

The homogenised paste was divided in different batches: one for the controls and 3 batches within the dried mint extract (ME) was added at different concentrations (%): C1 (1×MIC), C2 (3×MIC), and C3 (6×MIC). Ultimately, after adjusting the conditions of maturation of the sausages, another batch was performed; one for control and the other one for sausages with mint

extracts. In this report, the results of the control and the sausages supplemented with C2 mint extract were presented.

Dried cattle natural casings (20-25) cm of length and about 4-5 cm of diameter) were used. Prior to embedding, the casings were soaked in potable water and vinegar for approximately two days. The stuffing of the sausages was done after resting period while avoiding the air bubbles in the mass that can cause unwanted oxidation using kitchen aid machine.

Figure 18: Methodology applied to prepare the sausages (collaboration between Polytechnic Institute of Bragança & university of Manouba, internships of BenHmidène I)

After 24 h in 5 °C cold chamber, the inoculated and non-inoculated (control) sausages were tied by hand with strings, about 10 cm in length for each link, then hanged in the controlled humid chamber to dry until reaching the desired dehydration.

Relative humidity and temperature ranges selected considering the Tunisian traditional processing conditions during the wintertime as indicated in the **Table 11**.

Table 11. Relative humidity and temperature during the maturation and drying steps

Conditions	Maturation	Convective Drying
RH	97%	50-63%
Temperature of drying	10°C	27°C
Duration	24 hours	15 days

The inoculation procedure was performed in such a way that product formulation is not changed. Therefore, the inoculation was performed by using a laminar flow cabinet to avoid contamination with other microorganisms. The inoculum volume did not exceed 1% of the product weight or volume and was injected into the sausages (25cm/ 75g each) prepared manually by piercing with a syringe needle at 6 different points of the sausage. After removal from the constant humidity chamber, the sausage samples were peeled and cut into smaller pieces aseptically for enumeration of the bacteria. As for the first point of analysis, the inoculated sausages were directly stomached when analysing and the level of contamination was confirmed by testing control positive unit after the inoculation. *L. monocytogenes* WDCM 00019, obtained from the Polytechnic Institute of Bragança stock collection, was used for all experiments. A loop of culture kept on Nutrient Agar slants was inoculated separately in 10 mL of TSB broth. Broth tubes were incubated at 37 °C for 16 h, following two successive inoculations, to achieve a concentration of approximately 10⁸ CFU/mL, then adjusted to the desired concentration by dilution.

L. monocytogenes and Lactic Acid Bacteria (LAB) were detected and quantified by ISO methods (ISO 11290 and ISO 15214, respectively). The pH and a_w of samples were also measured during the drying step. The experiments were repeated three times.

6.2. Summary of Results for Fermented Dried Sausage

The main results of the fate studies conducted before adjusting the conditions of maturation are illustrated in **Figure 19**, for control C and the sausages treated with dried mint extract C1, C2, and C3. The duration of each study was adjusted to the artisanal product desired final characterization and water activity.

Figure 19A. *Listeria* behaviour curves in the presence of different concentrations of ME (mg/mL). (Bleu coloured line: control • grey **grey** coloured line C1 • red coloured line: C2 • yellow coloured line: C3). The lines represent the fit of experimental data to the fitting model. (1) (2) *L. monocytogenes* growth curves.

Figure 19B. Lactic acid bacteria kinetic curves in the presence of different concentrations of ME (mg/mL). (Bleu coloured line: control • grey coloured line C1 • red coloured line: C2 • yellow coloured line: C3). The lines represent the fit of experimental data to the fitting model. (1) (2) *L. monocytogenes* growth curves

The results show that all samples supported the growth of *L. monocytogenes* and spontaneously LAB. Overall, the pH and the water activity of samples dropped over the drying in 27°C simultaneously with the increase of the LAB suggesting the start of the natural fermentation process as indicated in **Figure 20 and 21**. When inoculated to sausage samples both LAB (**Figure 19B**) and *L. monocytogenes* (**Figure 19A**) grew well during fermentation drying process, showing exponential growth followed by entry into the decay phase.

The bacterial growth curves shown in **Figure 19** clearly suggest that meat sausages and the fermentation condition (27 °C, 60-50% relative humidity) can support the growth of LAB or *L. monocytogenes* when it was individually inoculated to the samples.

The initial concentration of LAB was about 4.5–5 log CFU/g, which effectively established its growth and overwhelmed the inoculated *L. monocytogenes* in meat sausages. Indeed, for the control batch, the growth of *L. monocytogenes* during 7 days of storage was approximately 2.47 log CFU/g. LAB growth potential was higher, with an increase of 6.94 log CFU/g after 9 days.

Analogously, *L. monocytogenes*, even with a very high level of extract, succeeded to establish its growth reaching its maximum approximately at 8 log CFU/g. Its population gradually declined (< 2.5 log CFU/g) till the end of process.

Figure 20. Profiles of pH values obtained in three analysis repetitions both of controls samples (nonoptimized process green coloured line and optimized process blue coloured line) and mint extract added samples (C2 in the optimized process in red coloured line) during drying.

Figure 21. Changes in water activity during fermentation and drying phases while temperature adjustment. The lines represent the fit of experimental data.

Until the 7th day, the inactivation of *L. monocytogenes* is observed. A decrease of 4.72 log CFU/g was measured at 15th day of drying. In the sausages prepared with mint extract C3 (Fig 2.A), *L. monocytogenes* revealed a growth potential of 2.25 log CFU/g after 7 days of drying and a significant drop (from day 7 to day 15) of 4.37 log CFU/g at 15 days of drying in the inactivation phase. The LAB reached a maximum average increase of 6.33 log CFU/g from day 1 to day 9 and a decrease of 3.45 log CFU/g from day 1 to day 15 of the process. The drop in pH and water activity values during the drying was similar to that observed in control batch and favourable after adjustment for microbiological stability of the end product ($a_w < 0.66$) as indicated in **Figure 20 and 21**.

Overall, there is two distinguished phases in both productions; growth (log phase) and inactivation phase for the selected pathogen. The growth of *L. monocytogenes* increased with change of the temperature in 24 h reaching its maximum after 7 days of drying at 27C. The growth rates of *L. monocytogenes* were slightly affected by the incorporation of the mint extract before adjustments **Figure 22**.

Figure 22. Changes in the populations of LAB and *L. monocytogenes* during simultaneously fermentation and drying of sausages after adjustment (A. control and B. sausages with C2 mint extract). The lines represent the modelling fit of experimental data.

Furthermore, *L. monocytogenes* maximum population density decreased and was followed by an increase in the LAB population suggesting a competition between the pathogen and LAB.

The addition of plant extract as demonstrated in these fate studies showed a positive effect on the safety of naturally fermented dry sausage. However, the beneficial effect of adding extracts was most evident after adjustment of the maturation phase. The viability of *L. monocytogenes* was compromised. A decreasing trend was observed, with increasing maximum specific inactivation rate, after surviving for some time. The statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) as indicated in **Figure 22A and 22B**. A reduction of 2.02 log UFC/g was noted after 150 hours in sausages treated with C2 of mint extract. Concerning LAB behaviour, homogeneous LAB populations were obtained at the final of the drying stage (from 7.6 to 8.4 log CFU/g), regardless of the sample type. Mint extract not only decreased the growth rate of *L. monocytogenes* (**Figure 22**), but it also protected the LAB from the lethal effects as reported in many studies.

6.3. Summary of Material & Methods for Fermented milk

Lab scale fermented milk was prepared using raw cow milk. Raw milk (5 L) was obtained from local farm and was pasteurized at 80°C/15 min and cooled to 37 °C. This was followed by the addition of *L. paracasei* OWS 23: (SAMN27689332), an autochthonous Lactic bacteria strain at 7-log CFU level. The milk was then mixed and left to ferment at 37°C for ~18h. Once the resulting curdled milk was obtained; it was manually shaken and divided in different samples (**Figure 23**). Citrus lemon peel extract was obtained by ETOH 80% solvent extraction at 1:10 (citrus powder/solvent) ratio at 40°C for 30 min with a rotational speed of 200 rpm using an orbital shaker. The supernatants of three extractions obtained after centrifugation were combined, filtered and lyophilized. *L. monocytogenes* from stock cultures was activated twice in BHI broth at 37 °C for 16-18h and adopted to storage temperature for three days and then diluted to 6 log CFU/ mL. The obtained fermented milk was inoculated with *L. monocytogenes* to obtain a concentration of ~ 5 log CFU/ mL. 4 different samples were prepared: Fermented milk inoculated by *L. monocytogenes* and supplemented by Citrus extract at 2*MIC level, control sample (Fermented milk+ *L. monocytogenes*) not supplemented with lemon extract and fermented milk without *L. monocytogenes* supplemented or no with lemon extract were used for physicochemical analysis. Inoculated fermented milk were divided in aliquots of 60 mL in sterile glass containers and incubated at 4 °C for 7 days. Microbiological and chemical analyses were performed each day during incubation; for that at each sampling point a container of 50 mL of fermented milk spiked or not with *Listeria* and supplemented or not with lemon extract, were used for analyses.

Fermented milk samples were analyzed for *L. monocytogenes*, LAB, the total bacteria count (TBC), pH, and lactic acid content. All experiments and analyses were triplicated.

Figure 23. Scheme of the methodology applied to obtain Lab scale fermented milk
(Collaboration UNIBO, Italy and ISBST, Tunisia)

6.4 Summary of Results for Fermented milk

For fermented milk, data changes in *Listeria*, LM, lactic acid bacteria, LAB and total bacteria count, TBC, are reported in **Figure 24 A, B and C**, respectively. A gradual decrease was observed in *Listeria* tendency between samples supplemented or not with extract after approximately 48 h of product cold storage for both types of samples until 168 h. The count started at 5.8 log CFU/mL and reached 4.88 for fermented milk without citrus extract and 3.76 log CFU/mL for fermented milk supplemented with citrus lemon extract. On the other hand, LAB count increase slightly during cold storage from 6.1 to 6.6 log CFU/mL for control sample and from 5.9 to 6.28 log CFU/mL for fermented milk with extract. The obtained results showed that LAB continued to show its homogeneous behavior during cold storage period. In the case of TBC, a decrease in the microbial load was noted with lower values obtained for fermented milk supplemented with lemon peel extract.

(A)

(B)

(C)

Figure 24. Trends of *L. monocytogenes* (A), lactic acid bacteria, LAB, (B) and total mesophilic bacteria, TBC (C) during the fermented milk storage at 4°C with (red lines) and without citrus lemon extract (black lines)

This result may explain the effect of citrus peel lemon extract (2×CMI) on the behavior of the tested pathogenic bacteria (*L. monocytogenes*). The decrease of *Listeria* load during storage could also be attributed to the low level of pH in fermented milk and to bio-preservative metabolites of lactic acid content such as organic acid.

Before storage, the pH value of fermented milk was 4.5 while at the end of storage, the pH decreases to 4.4-4.39 for fermented milk without and with lemon peel extract respectively (**Figure 25A**). At the same time, an increase of lactic acid content from 0.65 to 0.73-0.82 g/L during storage was observed (**Figure 25B**). The supplementation with lemon peel extract induces an increase in LAB count and lactic acid production. The decrease in pH and the increase of lactic acid during the production and storage of fermented milk is expected for this dairy product. The results underline a possible mutual effect of *L. paracasei* and citrus lemon peel extract as antimicrobial agents. The use of lactic bacteria and plant extract seems to be a tool for the control of pathogen growth during storage of fermented milk.

Fig. 25. pH (A) and acidity (B) changes during storage at 4°C of fermented milk with (red lines) or without (black lines) citrus lemon extract (2 × CMI)

7. Partner AUA

7.1. Summary of Material & Methods

7.1.1. Inoculum preparation

All strains of *L. monocytogenes* and *Salmonella* spp. were stored at -20°C with 20% glycerol in TSB. A hundred (100) µL of stock solution were transferred to 10 mL TSB for 24 h at 37 °C and subsequently, 100 µL of each overnight culture were incubated in fresh TSB for 18 h at 37 °C. Strains of each pathogen were harvested by centrifugation (3600rpm; 10 min; 4 °C) (Megafuge 1.0 R, Heraeus, Buckinghamshire, England), washed twice and re-suspended in 10 mL of ¼ strength Ringers' solution (OXOID, UK). Finally, the population of each strain per pathogen was enumerated at approximately 9.0 log CFU/mL by spread plating on Tryptone Soya Agar (TSA, OXOID, UK).

7.1.2. Incorporation of Oregano essential oil (OEO) into liposomes and/ or β-cyclodextrins

The encapsulation of OEO in β-CD (Scheme 1) was performed with the co-precipitation method (Garcia-Sotero et al., 2019) in two different ratios of OEO:β-CDs (1:99 and 8:92), whereas for the incorporation of OEO into liposomes (Scheme 2) the thin-film hydration method was applied (Moghimpour et al., 2012).

7.1.3. Preparation of whey protein film

Whey protein film (WPI) was prepared according to the method previously described by (Alizadeh Sani et al., 2017) with some modifications. Oregano essential oil (OEO; *Origanum vulgare* sp. *Hirtum*, Mandragoras, Greece) at 1.5 and 2.5% (w/w) ratios (incorporated into water-glycerol solutions) was added to the film-forming solutions in order WPI-OEO-1.5% and WPI-OEO-2.5% films to be formed. WPI-films without OEO (WPI) to serve as controls, were also prepared following the same procedure.

7.1.4. *In situ* application of antimicrobials

- **In katiki cheece**

“Katiki” cheese (fat: 13%, protein: 10%, salt: 1%) purchased from a local market was divided into samples of 80 g under into sterile containers of 120 mL (F.L. MEDICAL, Italy) under aseptic conditions. Samples were inoculated with an appropriate amount of a mixture of three strains *L.monocytogenes* and *Salmonella spp.*, respectively. The *L.monocytogenes* and *Salmonella spp.* strains inoculated to an initial population of 10^6 CFU/g. Free OEO (F_OEO), OEO encapsulated in liposomes (Lip_OEO) and/or in β - cyclodextrins (OEO-bCDs) were added at each sample at concentration 0.88% (v/v). Samples with no essential oil (Control), or empty liposomes (Lip_Control) and β CDs, were used as controls. The samples for katiki cheese were kept at 7°C for 21 days for *L.monocytogenes* and 17 days for *Salmonella spp.* The above procedures were performed twice, and all samples were analyzed in duplicate.

- **On noumboulo sausage slices**

Nouboulo sausage used in this study was obtained from a local store. The noumboulo was processed on a meat slicer preset to yield 4- to 5-g slices and transferred to the laboratory for surface inoculation. The upper surface of each slice was inoculated with 20 μ L of the *L. monocytogenes* by spreading the inoculum over the entire surface with a sterile bent glass rod. Following a 2-min resting period for bacterial attachment, the slices were flipped over, and the other side of the slide was inoculated (Gounadaki et al., 2007). Following this procedure, the inoculum (6 Log CFU/g) that was used is capable to be absorbed by the noumboulo slices without affecting the physicochemical properties of the product. After inoculation, two inoculated noumboulo slices (4-5 g) were placed in-between of three WPI-films (sandwich like) and the whole set were placed into a clear polyethylene bag (Flexo-Vacuum Pe06, Flexopack Societe Anonyme Commercial and Indrusial Plastics). Samples were then vacuum packed (Vacuum packer, LERICA, C312, Italy) and stored at 10 °C for 33 days. Samples containing WPI-films without OEO and without WPI films served as controls. The above procedures were performed twice, and the samples were analyzed in duplicate.

7.1.5. Microbiological analysis of samples

At specific time intervals, two samples were removed from storage and analyzed independently. Serial decimal dilutions were performed in Ringer's solution and the samples were poured or spread on the following media: ALOA (*L.monocytogenes*) incubated at 37°C for 48h, XLD (*Salmonella spp.*) incubated at 37°C for 24h, RBC (yeasts & moulds) incubated at 25°C for 72h and MRS (lactic acid bacteria) incubated at 30°C for 72h. 42

7.2. Summary of Results

In *Katiki* cheese, regardless of the application method of OEO (as free OEO, or encapsulated in liposomes or β -cyclodextrins), *Salmonella* spp. appeared to be more sensitive compared to *L. monocytogenes* (Figure 26). Incorporation of OEO into different inclusion complexes such as β -cyclodextrins and/or liposome, exhibited different antimicrobial activity against the pathogens tested (Figure 26).

Figure 26. Survival curves (mean values \pm standard deviations, $n=4$) of *Listeria monocytogenes* (a, b, c, d) and *Salmonella* spp. (e, f, g, h) cocktail strains in “*Katiki*” cheese containing **0.88%** (v/v) of **free** and **encapsulated OEO** during aerobic storage at 7 °C

More specifically, OEO at 0.88% (v/v) reduced the levels of *L.monocytogenes* in katiki cheese, in the following order of rate and magnitude of log reductions: free OEO at 0.88% > OEO at 0.88% in β -CDs at the 8:92 ratio >> OEO at 0.88% in Liposomes (Figure 26). *Salmonella*

populations were reduced by OEO in katiki cheese, as follows:: Free OEO at 0.88% > OEO at 0.88% in β -CDs at the 8:92 ratio > OEO at 0.88% in β -CDs at the 1:99 ratio > OEO at 0.88% in Liposomes (**Figure 26**). The results are indicative of the efficiency of encapsulated OEO as a means to control of pathogens in *katiki* cheese.

In the case of *noumboulo* sausage, incorporation of OEO into edible WPI films was able to cause a 2 log reduction in the levels of *L. monocytogenes*, regardless of the OEO concentration (**Figure 27**).

Figure-27. Survival curves of *L. monocytogenes* cocktail strains on noumboulo slices packaged under vacuum with WPI films with 1.5% and 2.5% OEO and stored at 10°C for 33 days.

D values (data shown in WP 6.1 & 6.2) were found to be depended on the OEO concentration incorporated into the film. The higher the OEO concentration the lower the D value and the higher the total reduction in the levels of *L. monocytogenes* (Figure 2). The results are indicative of the potential edible films to increase product safety, during storage.